

Magnesium supplementation improves ovarian folliculogenesis in type 1 diabetes mellitus

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Abstract

Introduction: Type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) is associated with oxidative stress and metabolic dysfunction, contributing to impaired ovarian folliculogenesis and reproductive dysfunction. Meanwhile, magnesium plays a crucial role in improving insulin sensitivity, reducing oxidative stress, and supporting cellular functions.

Objective: This study aimed to evaluate the effects of magnesium supplementation, insulin therapy, and their combination on metabolic biomarkers, oxidative stress, and ovarian folliculogenesis in streptozotocin (STZ)-induced T1DM rats.

Methods: A total of 35 female Wistar rats were divided into five groups, namely P1 (control), P2 (diabetic untreated), P3 (diabetic + insulin 4 IU/200 g/day), P4 (diabetic + magnesium 300 mg/kg/day), and P5 (diabetic + insulin + magnesium). The treatments were administered for 21 days. Fasting blood glucose (FBG), serum insulin, IGF-1, HER2/neu, and malondialdehyde (MDA) levels were measured. Ovarian follicle counts and histopathological evaluations were conducted to assess folliculogenesis.

Results: Magnesium (P4) and combination therapy (P5) significantly improved serum insulin levels (P4: 3.36 ± 0.46 mIU/L; P5: 4.19 ± 0.29 mIU/L; control: 4.05 ± 0.37 mIU/L), reduced MDA concentrations (P4: 0.94 ± 0.16 nmol/mL; P5: 0.97 ± 0.14 nmol/mL; control: 0.94 ± 0.30 nmol/mL), and restored IGF-1 levels (P5: 54.51 ± 4.45 ng/mL; control: 55.20 ± 9.69 ng/mL). Histopathological analysis showed significant follicular restoration in P5, with counts of primary, secondary, and Graafian follicles approaching normal levels (P5: 18.57 ± 2.37 ; control: 22.14 ± 1.35).

Conclusion: Magnesium supplementation, particularly in combination with insulin, reduced oxidative stress, restored metabolic biomarkers, and improved ovarian folliculogenesis in T1DM. This combination therapy offers a promising approach for managing diabetes-related reproductive dysfunction.

Keywords

insulin therapy, magnesium, oxidative stress, ovarian folliculogenesis, type 1 diabetes mellitus

Introduction

Type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) is a chronic autoimmune condition characterized by insulin deficiency due to the destruction of pancreatic β -cells. Although it can occur at any age, T1DM predominantly develops in children and young adults (American Diabetes Association 2009). In 2022, the International Diabetes Federation (IDF) reported 8.75 million cases of T1DM globally, including 1.52 million individuals under 20 years old (Magliano et al. 2022). Women with T1DM face distinct challenges, including a 40% higher risk of mortality and double the risk of vascular complications compared to men (Bak et al. 2023). These risks are compounded by significant reproductive dysfunctions, which affect up to 40% of women with T1DM throughout their lives. Young women with T1DM face problems such as delayed puberty, irregular menstruation, infertility, and early menopause (Arifin et al. 2019; Sundhani et al. 2022).

Ovarian problems in T1DM are complicated. Issues such as not having enough insulin, having too much sugar in the blood, and oxidative stress make it worse. Insulin is important because it helps keep the hypothalamic–pituitary–ovarian axis working properly. It is a co-gonadotropin and helps with folliculogenesis and steroidogenesis (Neirijnck et al. 2019). Insulin varies have receptors for insulin and insulin-like growth factor-1 (IGF-1). These activate important pathways like PI3K/Akt and MAPK, which are about cell growth, survival, and differentiation (Neirijnck et al. 2019; Piau et al. 2023). The mechanism of action for ovaries is disrupted when insulin signaling is inhibited due to deficiency or too much sugar in the blood. Follicles dying and other problems, such as granulosa cells breaking down and oocytes not maturing properly, may occur (Dri et al. 2021).

Oxidative stress gets worse when there are too many reactive oxygen species (ROS) and advanced glycation end-products (AGEs). This is important in how T1DM causes ovarian problems. Some ROS is normal and helps with processes like folliculogenesis and steroidogenesis (Dri et al. 2021). However, when ROS levels go too high, events such as granulosa cell death, inflammation, and damage to ovarian tissues may occur. Prolonged high blood sugar makes this worse by damaging mitochondria and the antioxidant system, which then harms reproductive health even more.

People with T1DM often do not have enough magnesium, which is tied to bad blood sugar control and higher oxidative stress. Magnesium is important for over 300 enzyme reactions, including how insulin receptors work and how glucose is processed. Low magnesium makes insulin resistance worse and lowers how much the body produces because it stops tyrosine kinase in insulin receptors from working well (Rodrigues et al. 2020; Younesi et al. 2022; Kusuma et al. 2024). Moreover, magnesium's antioxidant role helps with oxidative stress, which is a big reason for ovarian problems in T1DM (Morakinyo et al. 2018). Excessive ROS can harm follicles and oocytes, making fertility worse (Chutia and Lynrah 2015). Magnesium sup-

plementation may improve ovarian health by lowering oxidative stress and promoting follicle growth. However, its synergistic potential with insulin therapy in restoring ovarian folliculogenesis in T1DM remains largely unexplored, representing an important gap in reproductive endocrinology research. This could help the ovaries have more good-quality follicles and improve reproduction (Kim et al. 2010). Studies show magnesium supplements lower oxidative stress in diabetic models, which is good for ovarian health (Dasgupta et al. 2012; Hata et al. 2013).

Magnesium supplements can cause interaction with insulin and IGF systems. In general, IGF-1, or insulin-like growth factor-1, facilitates the growth of follicles. Magnesium boosts IGF-1, which helps with follicle growth and stops cells from dying (Barbagallo et al. 2014; Lin et al. 2016; Piau et al. 2023). It is also needed for IGF-1 to work effectively, facilitating ovarian follicle growth and maturation (Kumar et al. 2020).

This study aimed to examine how magnesium supplements affect follicle growth in rats with T1DM. Insulin levels, IGF-1, oxidative stress markers (ROS and malondialdehyde), and the number of ovarian follicles were evaluated.

Materials and methods

Chemicals and reagents

The chemicals used in this study were magnesium chloride (Nutricost), insulin (Lantus, 100 IU/mL), ketamine, xylazine, and streptozotocin (STZ), all obtained from standard sources and of analytical grade. Additional materials included ELISA kits for insulin (Cat. No. E0707Ra), IGF-1 (Cat. No. E0709Ra), HER2/neu (Cat. No. E2460Ra), and malondialdehyde (MDA) (Cat. No. E0156Ra), which were purchased from Bioassay Technology Laboratory (BT LAB).

Animal model and induction of type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM)

A total of 35 female Wistar rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) aged 6–8 weeks and weighing 170–200 g were bred and housed at the Laboratory for Research and Animal Testing Unit 4 (LPPT Unit 4), Universitas Gadjah Mada. The rats were kept in ventilated laboratory cages at a controlled room temperature (25–27 °C) and maintained on a 12-hour light–dark cycle with unrestricted access to standard pellet feed and water.

T1DM was induced in 28 rats through a single intraperitoneal injection of STZ at a dose of 65 mg/kg body weight, dissolved in citrate buffer (0.1 M, pH 4.5). Diabetes was confirmed three days after injection by measuring fasting blood glucose (FBG) levels using a photometer (Microlab 300, MERCK). Rats with FBG \geq 200 mg/dL were classified as diabetic and included in the experimental groups, while seven rats served as normal controls and received no STZ. Ethical approval for this study was granted by the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Sebelas Maret (Approval No. 96/UN27.06.11/KEP/EC/2024).

Experimental design

After a seven-day acclimatization period, rats were randomly assigned to five groups ($n = 7$ per group) using a computer-generated randomization sequence. Treatment allocation was concealed from the investigator responsible for outcome measurements. All treatments were administered by an investigator not involved in histopathological or biochemical assessments. Histological evaluations were performed by a veterinary pathologist blinded to the group assignments to minimize observation bias.

1. **Group 1 (P1):** Normal control, no STZ induction, placebo (distilled water).
2. **Group 2 (P2):** STZ-induced T1DM, placebo (distilled water).
3. **Group 3 (P3):** STZ-induced T1DM, subcutaneous insulin injections (4 IU/200 g body weight/day).
4. **Group 4 (P4):** STZ-induced T1DM, oral magnesium chloride supplementation (300 mg/kg body weight/day).
5. **Group 5 (P5):** STZ-induced T1DM, insulin (4 IU/200 g body weight/day), and magnesium chloride (300 mg/kg body weight/day).

Treatments were administered daily for 21 days. Insulin was given subcutaneously, while magnesium chloride was given orally through gavage. At the end of the treatment period, rats were euthanized under general anesthesia induced by ketamine (100 mg/kg) and xylazine (15 mg/kg). Blood and ovarian tissue samples were collected for biochemical and histological analyses.

Sample collection and preparation

To collect blood samples, rats were euthanized by cardiac puncture. Approximately 5 mL of blood was drawn from the heart of each rat and collected into sterile specimen bottles. The blood was allowed to clot at room temperature for 30 minutes, then centrifuged at 3,000 g for 20 minutes to separate the serum. The resulting serum was stored at -80°C until analysis of insulin and IGF-1 levels. Following blood collection, the ovaries were carefully excised. Half of each ovary was rinsed in ice-cold phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4) to remove excess blood, weighed, and homogenized in PBS at a ratio of 1:9 (tissue: PBS) using a glass homogenizer on ice. The homogenate was sonicated to further disrupt the cells and centrifuged at 5,000 g for five minutes. The supernatant was collected and stored at -80°C for subsequent analysis of HER2/neu and MDA levels. The other half of the ovarian tissue was fixed in 10% formalin for 48 hours, followed by paraffin embedding. Tissue sections of 5–10 μm were cut and stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) for histological evaluation. These sections were examined under a light microscope at 400 \times magnification to assess folliculogenesis, including the identification and quantification of primary, secondary, and tertiary follicles and corpus luteum.

Biomarker assays

Biomarker levels in serum and ovarian tissue were assessed using commercially available ELISA kits. The following biomarkers were measured:

- **Insulin:** Serum insulin levels were quantified using the Rat Insulin ELISA Kit (Bioassay Technology Laboratory, Cat. No. E0707Ra).
- **IGF-1:** Serum IGF-1 levels were measured using the Rat IGF-1 ELISA Kit (Bioassay Technology Laboratory, Cat. No. E0709Ra).
- **HER2/Neu:** Ovarian HER2/neu levels were quantified using the Rat HER2/neu ELISA Kit (Bioassay Technology Laboratory, Cat. No. E2460Ra).
- **MDA:** Ovarian malondialdehyde (MDA) levels, a marker of oxidative stress, were measured using the Rat MDA ELISA Kit (Bioassay Technology Laboratory, Cat. No. E0156Ra).

The ELISA assays were conducted according to the manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, samples and standards were prepared, and the plates were incubated with the appropriate antibodies for 1 hour at 37°C . After washing, substrate solutions were added, and the plates were incubated for an additional 10 minutes. Absorbance was measured at 450 nm using a microplate reader.

Histological analysis

The ovarian tissue sections were examined using light microscopy at 400 \times magnification. The number of ovarian follicles at different developmental stages (primary, secondary, tertiary, and Graafian follicles) was counted. Additionally, the presence of primary, secondary, and Graafian follicles was recorded. The histological evaluation was carried out at the Pathology Laboratory, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Universitas Gadjah Mada.

Statistical analysis

The data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). The normality of the data was assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk test. Statistical comparisons between groups were made using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by the post-hoc Duncan's multiple range test for pairwise comparisons. Statistical significance was considered at $p < 0.05$. All data analyses were performed using SPSS version 26.0.

Results

Fasting blood glucose (FBG) levels

The FBG levels of all experimental groups were measured three days after STZ induction to confirm the development of T1DM. As shown in Table 1, the FBG levels in all STZ-induced groups (P2–P5) were significantly higher than in the normal control (P1) ($p < 0.0001$). Specifically,

Table 1. Comparison of FBG, insulin, IGF-1, HER2/neu, and MDA levels across groups.

Group	FBG (mg/dL)	Insulin (mIU/L)	IGF-1 (ng/mL)	HER2/Neu ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	MDA (nmol/mL)
P1	144.61 \pm 31.16a	4.05 \pm 0.37a	55.20 \pm 9.69a	9.45 \pm 2.13a	0.94 \pm 0.30a
P2	435.77 \pm 35.03b	2.41 \pm 0.15b	40.95 \pm 2.96b	4.47 \pm 0.76b	1.96 \pm 0.54b
P3	462.71 \pm 24.94b	3.75 \pm 0.71c	50.13 \pm 3.43a	6.79 \pm 1.62c	1.01 \pm 0.21a
P4	413.36 \pm 23.76b	3.36 \pm 0.46c	50.50 \pm 2.56a	7.58 \pm 1.56ac	0.94 \pm 0.16a
P5	454.31 \pm 34.76b	4.19 \pm 0.29a	54.51 \pm 4.45a	7.46 \pm 2.48ac	0.97 \pm 0.14a

Note: Different superscripts within a column indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

the FBG levels in the STZ-induced groups exceeded 400 mg/dL, a value well above the diabetic threshold of 200 mg/dL, confirming successful induction of T1DM. The FBG values among the STZ-induced groups (P2–P5) were comparable, with no significant differences observed between them ($p > 0.05$). These results validated the use of these rats as diabetic models for subsequent biomarker and histological analysis.

Biomarker assays

The effects of magnesium supplementation and insulin therapy on key biomarkers, including serum insulin, IGF-1, HER2/neu, and MDA, are summarized in Table 1 and visualized in Fig. 1. These biomarkers reflect metabolic status, oxidative stress, and ovarian health in STZ-induced diabetic rats.

Serum insulin levels showed significant differences across the groups ($p < 0.0001$). Diabetic rats in the untreated group (P2) had significantly lower insulin levels (2.41 \pm 0.15 mIU/L) compared to the normal control group (P1:

4.05 \pm 0.37 mIU/L). Treatment with insulin alone (P3) or magnesium supplementation (P4) partially restored insulin levels, but the combination therapy (P5) proved most effective. Insulin levels in P5 (4.19 \pm 0.29 mIU/L) were comparable to those in the normal control group (P1), with no significant differences between these groups ($p > 0.05$). This underscores the synergistic effect of insulin and magnesium in regulating blood glucose and improving pancreatic function. For IGF-1, the same sort of trend was observed, with significant differences between groups ($p < 0.0001$). IGF-1 was lowest in the untreated diabetic rats (P2: 40.95 \pm 2.96 ng/mL). Insulin (P3) and magnesium (P4) caused improvement, and P5 (combination therapy) restored IGF-1 levels almost back to normal (54.51 \pm 4.45 ng/mL), close to the control group (P1: 55.20 \pm 9.69 ng/mL). This shows that magnesium, with insulin, supports IGF-1, which is important for follicle growth and overall health.

Combination therapy in P5 restored IGF-1 levels to near-normal values (54.51 \pm 4.45 ng/mL), closely approximating those in the control group (P1: 55.20 \pm 9.69 ng/mL), suggesting magnesium, particularly in combination with

Figure 1. Effects of treatments on biomarkers in STZ-induced T1DM rats. **a.** Serum insulin levels (mIU/L), **b.** Serum IGF-1 levels (ng/mL), **c.** Ovarian HER2/neu levels ($\mu\text{g/mL}$), and **d.** Ovarian MDA levels (nmol/mL) across treatment groups. Data are expressed as mean \pm SD. Different superscripts indicate significant differences between groups ($p < 0.05$, one-way ANOVA with Duncan's post-hoc test). Treatment groups: P1 (normal control), P2 (STZ-induced untreated), P3 (STZ-induced + insulin), P4 (STZ-induced + magnesium), and P5 (STZ-induced + insulin + magnesium).

insulin, plays a crucial role in regulating IGF-1. It is a key factor in ovarian folliculogenesis and metabolic health. The treatments also significantly affected ovarian HER2/neu levels ($p < 0.0001$). The untreated diabetic group (P2) had substantially lower HER2/neu levels ($4.47 \pm 0.76 \mu\text{g/mL}$) compared to the normal control group (P1: $9.45 \pm 2.13 \mu\text{g/mL}$).

Magnesium supplementation (P4: $7.58 \pm 1.56 \mu\text{g/mL}$) and combination therapy (P5: $7.46 \pm 2.48 \mu\text{g/mL}$) significantly improved HER2/neu levels compared to P2. However, the HER2/neu levels in P4 and P5 were almost the same as in P1. This means magnesium might help ovarian receptors work better and ameliorate ovarian problems in diabetes. Malondialdehyde (MDA), which indicated oxidative stress, was higher in the untreated diabetic group (P2: $1.96 \pm 0.54 \text{ nmol/mL}$) than in the control group (P1: $0.94 \pm 0.30 \text{ nmol/mL}$).

Treatments with insulin alone (P3: $1.01 \pm 0.21 \text{ nmol/mL}$), magnesium (P4: $0.94 \pm 0.16 \text{ nmol/mL}$), or combination therapy (P5: $0.97 \pm 0.14 \text{ nmol/mL}$) significantly reduced MDA levels ($p < 0.0001$). The single magnesium treatment (P4) and the combination (P5) restored MDA levels to the normal control (P1). These results confirm the antioxidant potential of magnesium in combating oxidative stress caused by diabetes.

Ovarian folliculogenesis effect

The effects of treatments on ovarian follicle counts are summarized in Table 2 and visualized in Fig. 2. Ovarian follicle count serves as a key indicator of reproductive health and reflects the degree of restoration of ovarian function in diabetic rats.

Table 2. Comparison of ovarian follicle counts across groups.

Group	Follicle Count (Mean \pm SD)
P1	$22.14 \pm 1.35\text{a}$
P2	$9.14 \pm 2.04\text{b}$
P3	$14.00 \pm 1.41\text{c}$
P4	$14.43 \pm 2.07\text{c}$
P5	$18.57 \pm 2.37\text{d}$

Note: Different superscripts indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 2. Effects of treatments on ovarian follicle counts in STZ-induced T1DM rats. Ovarian follicle counts across treatment groups: P1 (normal control), P2 (STZ-induced untreated), P3 (STZ-induced + insulin), P4 (STZ-induced + magnesium), and P5 (STZ-induced + insulin + magnesium). Data are expressed as mean \pm SD. Different superscripts indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$). Combination therapy (P5) showed the highest restoration among STZ-induced groups.

Fig. 2 shows that the untreated diabetic group (P2) had a significantly lower ovarian follicle count (9.14 ± 2.04) than the normal control group (P1: 22.14 ± 1.35) ($p < 0.0001$). Insulin therapy (P3: 14.00 ± 1.41) and magnesium supplementation (P4: 14.43 ± 2.07) both significantly improved follicle counts compared to P2 ($p < 0.05$). However, combination therapy (P5: 18.57 ± 2.37) was the most effective intervention, resulting in follicle counts that closely approached those of the normal control group. These results demonstrate the synergistic effects of magnesium and insulin in promoting folliculogenesis and mitigating reproductive dysfunction in diabetic rats.

Histopathological evaluation of ovarian follicles

The histopathological analysis of ovarian tissues showed significant differences in follicular development across the treatment groups (Fig. 3). In the normal control group (P1), ovarian tissues demonstrated well-organized structures with a balanced presence of primary, secondary, and Graafian follicles. In contrast, the untreated diabetic group (P2) had disorganized ovarian architecture, with a marked reduction in the number of secondary and Graafian follicles as well as an increase in atretic follicles. These results confirm the detrimental effects of diabetes on ovarian histology. In the group that received insulin (P3), the ovaries showed partial improvement, with more secondary and Graafian follicles compared to P2. Magnesium supplementation (P4) also provided benefits, with healthier-looking follicles and reduced atresia. The combined treatment group (P5) had the best results, with ovarian structures resembling those of the normal control group (P1). This treatment markedly improved follicle development, with more secondary and Graafian follicles than in the insulin-only group (P3) or the magnesium-only group (P4).

Discussion

This study looked at how magnesium, insulin treatment, and using both together affect parameters such as metabolic biomarkers, oxidative stress, and ovarian follicle growth in rats with T1DM caused by STZ. The results showed that magnesium plays an important role in improving ovarian problems and oxidative stress caused by diabetes. It also points out that using magnesium along with insulin might have beneficial effects on both metabolism and reproductive health.

Metabolic regulation and insulin signaling

Diabetes mellitus is characterized by chronic hyperglycemia, which results from impaired insulin secretion or action (Merovci et al. 2021). In this study, untreated diabetic rats (P2) displayed significantly elevated fasting blood glucose (FBG) levels and reduced insulin levels, indicating β -cell destruction due to STZ-induced oxida-

Figure 3. Histopathological analysis of ovarian tissues across the treatment groups revealed distinct follicular stages. Representative ovarian tissue sections highlighted primary follicles (green arrows), secondary follicles (blue arrows), and Graafian follicles (red arrows) in the following groups: (A) P1 (normal control), (B) P2 (untreated diabetic), (C) P3 (diabetic + insulin), (D) P4 (diabetic + magnesium), and (E) P5 (diabetic + insulin + magnesium). The combination therapy group (P5) demonstrated the most significant restoration of follicular development.

tive stress. These results match an earlier study that linked hyperglycemia in T1DM to oxidative stress and inflammation, which aggravates insulin resistance and disrupts β -cell function (Davies et al. 2022).

Insulin therapy (P3) helped increase serum insulin levels, but magnesium (P4) improved them further by enhancing insulin sensitivity and reducing oxidative stress (Massaro et al. 2016). When both therapies were combined (P5), insulin levels were nearly normalized, showing a stronger effect (Qi et al. 2023). Magnesium works by increasing insulin receptor sensitivity, modulating tyrosine kinase activity, and improving glucose transport, and this study shows that it could be a useful treatment for T1DM (Islam and Nyholt 2022). In both magnesium-treated (P4) and combined therapy (P5) groups, IGF-1 levels rose significantly (Nagao et al. 2021). IGF-1 helps regulate glucose metabolism and supports follicle growth in the ovaries (Zhang et al. 2023). The fact that magnesium restored IGF-1 indicates that it could help regulate endocrine signaling, probably through its antioxidant effects and modulation of the insulin/IGF-1 pathway (Abozaid et al. 2023).

Oxidative stress and HER2/neu regulation

Oxidative stress is a critical pathogenic factor in diabetes, contributing to structural and functional impairment of ovarian tissue (Yang et al. 2021). Untreated diabetic rats (P2) had high MDA levels, indicating significant lipid and

cellular damage. However, magnesium (P4) and combination therapy (P5) reduced MDA levels (Zhang et al. 2023). This is probably because magnesium can mitigate oxidative stress by scavenging reactive oxygen species (ROS) and preventing lipid peroxidation (Parcheta et al. 2021).

Magnesium also improved HER2/neu levels in P4 and P5, suggesting that it supports receptor function and cellular signaling (Slezak et al. 2024). HER2/neu is important for cell survival and growth, particularly in the ovaries, where it contributes to follicular development (Abdel Hamid et al. 2022). In untreated diabetic rats, receptor expression was lower, showing damage from oxidative stress. However, magnesium treatment countered this effect and reduced cell death (Bhatti et al. 2022). By lowering MDA levels and restoring HER2/neu expression, magnesium alleviated oxidative stress and supported ovarian cell viability. These findings suggest that magnesium may mitigate diabetes-induced cellular damage by attenuating oxidative stress and preserving ovarian function (Bhatti et al. 2022).

Ovarian folliculogenesis and synergistic effects

Diabetes causes oxidative stress, which disrupts ovarian function. In rats, this resulted in fewer follicles and more follicular atresia in the untreated group (P2) (Kanak et al. 2024). This study looked at tissue samples and found that magnesium (P4) and insulin (P3) helped improve

follicular development and restored follicle counts, including primary, secondary, and Graafian follicles (Wang 2020). When both treatments were used together (P5), the effect was strongest, almost comparable to the control group (P1) (Wang 2020). This shows that magnesium and insulin together help restore ovarian structure and function (Sengupta et al. 2024). Magnesium may promote follicular growth by preventing granulosa cell death and reducing oxidative stress in the ovaries (Kanafchian et al. 2020). Insulin also promotes follicular growth by enhancing gonadotropin signaling and supporting steroidogenesis (Ipsa et al. 2019). When both are used together, the effects are amplified, as magnesium enhances insulin's action by increasing ovarian steroid production and improving signaling.

Implications for therapeutic strategies

The results highlight the importance of addressing oxidative stress and insulin resistance in managing diabetes and its effects on reproduction. Insulin therapy is a mainstay in diabetes treatment, but adding magnesium may further improve insulin sensitivity, reduce oxidative stress, and support ovarian health. Therefore, combined use of insulin and magnesium could be a promising strategy for addressing reproductive complications in people with T1DM. This study examined how magnesium influences factors such as HER2/neu, IGF-1, and MDA, which are directly implicated in oxidative stress and ovarian health. More clinical studies are needed to establish effective dosing, treatment duration, and long-term outcomes of using magnesium with insulin in patients with diabetes.

Limitations and future directions

Although this study provides valuable evidence of magnesium's benefits, there are limitations to consider. The short-term design may not capture long-term effects on ovarian function, and the use of an animal model may not fully replicate human pathophysiology. Future studies should investigate the molecular pathways underlying the protective effects of magnesium, particularly its interaction with insulin signaling and oxidative stress regulation. Long-term studies focusing on fertility outcomes, hormonal regulation, and pregnancy success rates are also needed.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study demonstrated the significant therapeutic potential of magnesium supplementation, both alone and in combination with insulin therapy, in alleviating diabetes-induced metabolic and reproductive dysfunction. Magnesium effectively improved insulin sensitivity, restored IGF-1 levels, reduced oxidative stress, and preserved ovarian folliculogenesis, while combination therapy provided synergistic benefits by normalizing

metabolic biomarkers, lowering oxidative damage, and enhancing ovarian architecture, including the development of primary, secondary, and Graafian follicles. These results highlight magnesium as a promising adjunctive therapy for managing the metabolic and reproductive complications of T1DM. Future clinical studies are essential to validate these findings and establish optimal therapeutic protocols, paving the way for improved outcomes in diabetic patients.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest associated with the material presented in this paper.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: No. 96/UN27.06.11/KEP/EC/2024

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization: AN, SS, AP; methodology: AN, SS, AL, VW; investigation: AN, SS, AL, VP, PD; data curation: SS, AP; writing – original draft preparation: AN, RC; writing – review and editing: AL, VW, PD; supervision: SS, AP; funding acquisition: AN. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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